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DEMONOPOLIZATION OF THE ENERGY MARKETS

ДЕМОНОПОЛИЗАЦИЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ РЫНКОВ

ENERGETIKA BOZORLARINI MONOPOLIYADAN CHIQRISH

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Abstract. The Russia-Ukraine war has affected the energy security of all countries in the EU's so-called Wider Black Sea Region (WBSA - which also includes the South Caucasus), but the conflict has had the greatest impact on the EU's main gas supplier - the Russian JSC Gazprom. The article discusses the process of demonopolization of the EU gas market. In particular, it is noted that the Russia-Ukraine war has disrupted global supply chains, but this provides a new opportunity for Azerbaijan. In particular, since the US and Europe have imposed sanctions on Russian oil and natural gas, Azerbaijan has a chance to increase gas exports through the «Southern Gas Corridor» (SGC), which passes through seven countries (including Georgia) and supplies gas to Turkey and South-Eastern Europe. Currently, Azerbaijan, through the SGC, supplies Turkey and Europe with 16 billion cubic meters of natural gas annually.

Key words: EU SGC, Gas pipelines, Energy security, Caspian Sea, Black Sea, Gazprom, SOCAR, LNG, Gas corridor.

Аннотация. Российско-Украинская война затронула энергетическую безопасность всех стран так называемого Обширного Черноморского региона

ЕС (WBSA- включает в себя также Южный Кавказ), но конфликт оказал наибольшее влияние на главного поставщика газа ЕС - российское АО «Газпром». В статье обсуждается процесс демонополизации рынка газа ЕС. В частности, отмечается, что российско-украинская война нарушила глобальные цепочки поставок, но это дает Азербайджану новую возможность. В частности, поскольку США и Европа ввели санкции против российской нефти и природного газа, у Азербайджана есть возможность увеличить экспорт газа через «Южный газовый коридор» (ЮГК), который проходит через семь стран (включая Грузию) и поставляет газ в Турцию и Юго-Восточную Европу. В настоящее время Азербайджан через ЮГК ежегодно поставляет Турции и Европе 16 миллиардов кубометров природного газа.

Ключевые слова: ЮГК ЕС, газопроводы, энергетическая безопасность, Каспийское море, Черное море, Газпром, SOCAR, СПГ, Газовый коридор.

Annotatsiya. Rossiya-Ukraina urushi Yevropa Ittifoqining keng Qora dengiz mintaqasi (WBSA - Janubiy Kavkazni ham o'z ichiga oladi) deb ataladigan barcha mamlakatlarning energiya xavfsizligiga ta'sir ko'rsatdi, ammo mojaro Yevropa Ittifoqining asosiy gaz yetkazib beruvchisi - Rossiyaning "Gazprom" AJga eng katta ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Maqolada Yevropa Ittifoqi gaz bozorini demonopolizatsiya qilish jarayoni muhokama qilinadi. Xususan, Rossiya-Ukraina urushi global ta'minot zanjirlarini uzgani, biroq bu Ozarbayjon uchun yangi imkoniyat ekani qayd etilgan. Xususan, AQSH va Yevropa Rossiya nefti va tabiiy gaziga qarshi sanksiyalar kiritgani sababli, Ozarbayjon yettita davlat (jumladan, Gruziya) orqali o'tib, Turkiya va Janubi-Sharqiy Yevropaga gaz yetkazib beruvchi "Janubiy gaz yo'lagi" (JGY) orqali gaz eksportini oshirish imkoniyatiga ega. Ayni paytda Ozarbayjon JGY orqali Turkiya va Yevropaga yiliga 16 milliard kub metr tabiiy gaz yetkazib bermoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: EI JGY, Gaz quvurlari, Energiya xavfsizligi, Kaspiy dengizi, Qora dengiz, Gazprom, SOCAR, Suyultirilgan gaz, Gaz koridori.

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Introduction. In order to meet the growing demand of the South-Eastern European gas market, Azerbaijan is developing new gas fields and is open to investments to expand the capacity of the SGC, in particular, by installing additional compressor stations in Georgia and Turkey, it will be possible to double the gas flow by 2027. However, in this region of Europe, the «Vertical Gas Corridor» project has been launched since the beginning of 2024, which will be a direct competitor to the «Southern Gas Corridor», and appropriate measures need to be taken to ensure the timely implementation of long-term gas supply contracts that the Shah Deniz consortium has already signed with European consumers.

The proposed «Vertical Gas Corridor» is a project that will directly challenge Russia's last remaining major gas pipeline Bratstvo - Brotherhood (Urengoy-Pomary-Uzhgorod route) into the heart of Europe.

Bringing non-Russian gas into southern and central Europe via the Southern Gas Corridor has been a long-standing aim of the EU, regional EU member states, Turkey and gas producers as far afield as Central Asia and the Middle East, albeit with significantly differing agendas. Many projects, often grandiose, have been proposed over the years, often falling foul of the complex political and economic interests which crisscross the region. Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 provided yet another twist to this Levantine Great Game, creating both new impetus for supply diversification and new infrastructure options as the Kremlin's control over the pipelines originally built to bring gas west and south from Russia weakened. Now, under plans hatched by southeast and central European states, the region's growing gas interconnectivity could take another significant step forward, further weakening Russian Gas Monopoly JSC Gazprom.

The natural gas has only recently, since the 70s of the last century, turned into one of the main types of fuel. At the beginning of this century, about 88-90% of natural gas was delivered by gas pipelines under long-term economic contracts directly from a specific supplier to a specific customer, the rest - by tankers, in the form of liquefied gas (LNG). In 2021, global LNG imports, according to the report of the International LNG Importers Group (GIIGNL), increased by 4.5% compared to the previous year and reached 513.7 billion cubic meters (372.3 million tons). The group's research notes that in 2021, the LNG already accounts for about 40% of the global gas market, with the rest coming through gas pipelines. In 2021, about 73% of the LNG (375 billion cubic meters, or 271.8 million tons) was imported by Asian countries. In addition, only 36.6% of the world's LNG volume was sold on the spot market, i.e. in small lots, - the rest was sold through long-term contracts, thereby neglecting the market mechanism of free price formation. Due to the Russia-Ukraine war, the European Union's gas supply from Gazprom's pipelines was interrupted and Brussels is desperately looking for alternative routes.

For the first time, the idea of such an alternative in the form of the «Trans-Caspian gas pipeline» was put forward by then US President Bill Clinton in 1996. However, due to the uncertainty of the status of the Caspian Sea and the lack of delimitation of its shelf boundaries, due to the conflicting position of Azerbaijan, Iran and Turkmenistan, this project was not implemented yet.

After the annexation of Crimea in 2014 by Russia, the construction of one of the components of the «Southern Gas Corridor» (SGC) supported by the European Union - the «White Stream» gas pipeline and the liquefied gas project AGRI (LNG) initiated in 2007 - «Azerbaijan-Georgia-Ukraine-Romania-Hungary Interconnector» was postponed for an indefinite time. It should be noted that these were the most promising projects for Georgia and Azerbaijan, since both of them turned aside not only Russia, but also Turkey and, accordingly, neutralized its transit hegemony.

This gas, passing through the SCP, was sent through the Trans-Anatolian gas pipeline and the Trans-Adriatic (TAP), from Turkey to Europe as one EU's South Gas Corridor (SGC).

The Russia-Ukraine war has disrupted global supply chains and weakened the world economy, but it provides a new opportunity for Azerbaijan. In particular, as the

US and Europe impose sanctions on Russian oil and natural gas, Azerbaijan has a chance to increase gas exports and in the coming years via the 3,500-kilometer Southern Gas Corridor (SGC), which runs through seven countries and supplies gas to southern Turkey. Azerbaijan currently supplies 10 billion cubic meters of gas to Europe and 6 billion cubic meters - to Turkey, through the SGC.

To meet the growing demand of Europe, Azerbaijan is also developing two new gas fields and is open to investment to expand the capacity of the SGC, in particular, by installing additional compressor stations, it will be possible to double the gas flow. However, according to the Azerbaijani Ministry of Economy, «reduced investment» from Europe may slow down the country's efforts to increase supply. Therefore:

- the role of the «Southern Gas Corridor» in the context of the Russia-Ukraine war, and, consequently, the transit importance of Georgia for the EU energy security will increase even more;

- the «corridor» will provide the Caspian countries with new, increased opportunities for the export of energy resources to the world market and will have a significant impact on the security and stability of the region;

The Vice Prime Minister, Minister of Economy of Georgia, Mr. Levan Davitashvili, stated at a briefing held on November 21, 2022 that the Georgian government is working on a project to supply gas from the Caspian Sea shore of Azerbaijan to Europe through Georgia. According to Mr. Levan Davitashvili the project, in which Azerbaijan, Romania and Hungary also participate, already have been started in 2015 and provides for a plan by which «...gas will be liquefied on the territory of Georgia, and then it will be re-gasified in Romania». Unfortunately, this project was stopped and had no further development», he said, adding that «...Europe is especially interested in alternative sources of gas supply, when everyone is talking about diversification of energy supply. This project has gained special relevance this year».

Mr. Levan Davitashvili noted that the evaluation of the project and the infrastructure in the territory of Georgia-Azerbaijan is underway. «It won't happen in a day or a year», he said, adding that «...first, we need to depict a complete picture...then we need to formulate a detailed action plan...and start implementing this plan step by step, including attracting investments».

At the same time Azerbaijan's oil is in decline, but gas is growing. The future of Azerbaijan and Georgia energy cooperation is with natural gas EU's SGC and the Black Sea LNG terminals. Special attention should be paid to the prospects of supplying liquefied natural gas from Azerbaijan via Kulevi, Georgia to Romania from the SOCAR's BST Ltd [18].

The Russia-Ukraine war had a negative impact on Russian natural gas exports to Europe, which in previous years, along with oil, was one of the most reliable sources of funding for the Russian budget (Fig. 1).

The figure shows how the volumes of both pipeline and liquefied natural gas (LNG) imports into the EU from its main partners changed in 2022-2023. It is clear that pipeline imports from Russia accounted for only 17% of all imports in 2023, i.e., they fell from 150 billion cubic meters to 43 billion cubic meters in two years. The

resulting deficit was largely compensated by the growing share of other partners: imports of liquefied natural gas (LNG) from the US to Europe increased from 18.9 billion cubic meters in 2021 to 56.2 billion cubic meters in 2023, and in 2024 year accounted for 40% of all LNG imports; pipeline gas imports from Norway increased from 79.5 billion cubic meters in 2021 to 87.7 billion cubic meters in 2023 ; Gas imports from British, Azerbaijani, and North African pipelines have also increased; as have imports from other partners - from 41.6 billion cubic meters in 2021 to 62 billion cubic meters in 2023, which is 3% of all pipeline gas imports.

Fig. 1. EU gas importers by the end of 2023 [11]

In the second quarter of 2022, Russia's share of Europe's natural gas imports was almost 23 percent, among other non-EU suppliers. In 2024 year, this share was lower than in all of 2021, when it was almost 40 percent. The decrease was due to Western sanctions against Russia for its invasion of Ukraine and a reduction in gas supplies to Europe by Gazprom. Germany was the main export destination for natural gas from Russia, and in 2021 it received 23.7 percent of the total volume of gas exported from the Russian Federation via pipelines. Turkey was next, receiving 13 percent of total Russian natural gas exports in 2021 (Extra-EU, 2024).

But in the conditions of war, Gazprom, the Russian energy giant, majority-owned by the Russian state, for the first time in a quarter of a century, announced in 2023 that it would ended with a loss of almost 7 billion \$. According to the European Commission, the share of Gazprom in the EU’s pipeline gas imports decreased from 40% in 2021 to 8% in 2023 (International. The news 2024). In 2023, the EU already received a large part of its liquefied natural gas (LNG) imports from the USA. If in 2021 the USA supplied 19 billion cubic meters of liquefied natural gas to EU member states, in 2023 this figure increased to 56.2 billion cubic meters, in 2023 Qatar also increased its exports of liquefied natural gas to Europe - to 15.5 billion cubic meters.

The largest supplier of pipeline gas to the EU is currently Norway, which has increased its gas sales from 79.5 billion cubic meters to 87.8 billion cubic meters in the last two years (Tim Wallace. The Telegraph 2024) . By country, the main suppliers of gas to the EU in 2023 were Norway and the United States. Norway provided almost 30% of all gas imports to Europe. Additional suppliers include North African countries, the United Kingdom and Qatar. A list showing the market shares and values (in billion cubic meters) for the various EU gas suppliers in 2023 is as follows:

Table 1

Shares of gas imports into the European Union in 2023 [12]

Country	Share	Volume
Norway	30.3%	87.8 billion cubic meters
USA	19.4%	56.2 billion cubic meters
North Africa	14.1%	41 billion cubic meters
Russia (pipeline)	8.7%	25.1 billion cubic meters
Russia (liquid LNG)	6.1%	17.8 billion cubic meters
Great Britain	5.7%	16.6 billion cubic meters
Qatar	5.3%	15.5 billion cubic meters
Other	10.3%	29.9 billion cubic meters

In parallel with the closure of Russian pipelines, the EU is increasing its imports of liquefied natural gas (LNG) by tanker. In 2023, the EU imported more than 120 billion cubic meters of LNG. In 2023, the United States was the largest supplier of LNG to the EU, accounting for almost 50% of total LNG imports. In 2023, imports from the United States increased threefold compared to 2021. The largest importers of LNG are in the EU (see Figures 2, 3, where LNG regasification terminals are shown): France, Spain, the Netherlands, Belgium, Italy. Figure 2 shows the geography of liquefied natural gas (LNG) regasification terminals along the EU’s sea coasts, while Figure 3 shows the pre-war share of Russian pipeline gas in EU imports, which fell from 40 % in 2021 to around 8% in 2023. Already by early 2024, the combined share of Russian pipeline gas and LNG accounted for less than 15% of total EU gas imports. The reduction in Russian gas consumption was made possible by the increase in US LNG imports and the decline in EU gas consumption.

Fig. 2. Geography of liquefied natural gas (LNG) regasification terminals along the EU coasts [13]

Fig. 3. Share of Russian pipeline gas in EU imports in 2021 year [14]

Already in 2021, global LNG imports, according to the report of the International LNG Importers Group (GIIGNL), increased by 4.5% compared to the previous year and amounted to 513.7 billion cubic meters (or 372.3 million tons). The study notes that in 2021 LNG already accounted for about 40% of the global gas market, the rest - through pipelines. In 2021, about 73% of LNG (375 billion cubic meters, or 271.8 million tons) was sold by Asian countries. In addition, only 36.6% of the world's LNG volume was sold on the spot market, i.e. in small batches, the rest –

under long-term contracts (M.Katkov, 2022), thus ignoring the free pricing mechanism and demonstrating a typical «horizontal concentration» (Georgian Competition Agency, gcc.a.gov.ge).

In addition, natural gas is a raw material for industry and is used to generate a quarter of global electricity generation. It is a universal, environmentally friendly fuel. Compared to other types of fuel, the rapid growth of its extraction is associated with environmental benefits, in particular air cleanliness and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, which have been given primary importance in the European Union since the 2018 Paris Summit. The above figures highlight that

By 2023, Gazprom's total revenue fell to 8.5 trillion rubles (30 percent), while domestic and foreign gas sales fell from 8.4 trillion rubles to 4.1 trillion rubles. The company's shares fell 4.4 percent year-on-year due to Western sanctions. Gazprom's revenue from gas sales outside Russia fell from 7.3 trillion rubles in 2022 to 2.9 trillion rubles in 2023. This decline, according to analysts, was due to Gazprom's loss of the European market in 2021-2023 (see Figure 4, where the only currently operating route through Ukraine, the Brotherhood, or Urengoy-Pomari-Uzhgorod, is in effect, the rest are pipelines stopped as a result of the war). Meanwhile, European countries have had greater success than expected in their search for an alternative to Gazprom (see Figure 2).

Fig. 4. Gazprom's European gas pipelines [15]

Analysts estimate that what was once Russia's main business - selling gas to Europe - has now become loss-making, which is partially offset by profits from the sale of Russian oil.

Moreover, by 2025, Gazprom's only remaining European export route (the Brotherhood pipeline, see Figure 4) is expected to be halved and its throughput will

drop to 12 billion cubic meters per year if gas transit via Ukraine is not resumed. Today, the futures contract on the European market, i.e. the price of gas for delivery in 2025, averages \$400 per thousand cubic meters, meaning that Gazprom will lose about \$3 billion annually, or 272 billion rubles, at current exchange rates, by losing sales via Ukraine.

Azerbaijani gas exports to Europe will double, while oil production will decrease. Accordingly, the market of South-Eastern Europe is gradually being taken over by Azerbaijani gas. In fact, Romania, which has been receiving Russian gas through the «Trans-Balkan gas pipeline» since the 1980s, has switched to Azerbaijani gas since 2023. The first supply agreement signed by the «State Oil Company of the Republic of Azerbaijan» (SOCAR) and the Romanian company Romgaz on February 3, 2023 expired on March 31, 2024. Under this contract, Romania received 1 billion cubic meters of gas. The supply was carried out via the Greece-Bulgaria Interconnector (IGB) from the TAP (Trans Adriatic Pipeline) exit point in Komotini (Greece), via the Bulgarian city of Stara Zagora to Romania and further via the Bulgaria-Romania-Hungary-Austria (BRUA) gas pipeline system (see Figure 5).

SOCAR of Azerbaijan expressed its willingness to extend the above-mentioned contract until 2026. This was decided on April 1, 2024, after the expiration of the contract, when Romanian Energy Minister Sebastian Ioan Burduia visited Azerbaijan. The discussions at the meetings touched upon the prospects for the supply of liquefied natural gas from Azerbaijan to Romania, with particular attention paid to the possibility of producing LNG at SOCAR's BST Ltd. terminal in the Georgian port of Kulevi, with subsequent transportation to the Romanian port of Constanta. This project is considered extremely important not only for strengthening Romania's energy security, but also for the energy security of the European Union as a whole. Romania and Georgia will become a transit corridor for Azerbaijani gas through the Black Sea to Europe, which is a good way for Brussels to break away from Turkey's monopolistic transit hegemony [18].

Brussels' cooperation with Baku on transit began in 2023, when the EU stopped receiving most of its Russian gas, and when European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen traveled to Baku to meet with Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev. They signed a 10 billion cubic meter gas supply agreement to ensure Europe's energy security. «Therefore, the EU has decided to diversify from Russia and turn to more reliable partners. And I am glad to include Azerbaijan among them,» von der Leyen said during a conversation with I. Aliyev. She addressed I. Aliyev: «You are indeed an important energy partner for us and you have always been reliable».

Later, at the opening ceremony of the Bulgaria-Serbia Interconnector (see Figure 3) in Nis, Serbia, President Aliyev announced that Azerbaijan is moving towards the ambitious goal of doubling its gas exports to Europe by 2027. This means that Azerbaijan will have to not only increase natural gas volumes, but also significantly expand the capacity of the three main pipelines of the Southern Gas Corridor (SGC), including the South Caucasus Gas Pipeline (SGP) through Georgia.

This corridor is a vital artery for transporting Azerbaijani gas from the Caspian Sea coast directly to southeastern European markets (see Figure 5).

Fig. 5. Southern Gas Corridor Interconnector Greece-Bulgaria [16]

To achieve this goal, Azerbaijani gas production and exports have already increased by the beginning of 2024. In particular, in 2024, Azerbaijan was the fourth largest gas supplier to the EU after Algeria, Norway, the United Kingdom and Russia. Italy, Greece and Bulgaria are the main consumers of Azerbaijani gas in South-Eastern Europe. In 2023, they increased their imports to record volumes - about 12.9 billion cubic meters, according to Eurostat data. Figure 3 shows that until 2022, the EU imported approximately 150 billion cubic meters of gas from Russia, of which approximately 25 billion cubic meters are still supplied to it through pipelines through Turkey («Blue and Turkish Streams») and Ukraine («Brotherhood»), so there is still a large unmet demand for gas.

The impact of gas trade on the global and regional levels, that is, socioeconomic aspects, have been studied less than similar processes in relation to other types of fuel. In particular, in the former Soviet Union, due to the need to transport gas from the vast expanses of Siberia to the European part of the country, the construction of powerful pipelines began as early as the 1960s. As a result, the level of gasification of the population of the then USSR exceeded even some developed countries that are members of the current European Union. Accordingly, the former USSR was represented in the European gas market by 5 powerful gas pipelines, to which the «Blue Stream» and «Turkish Stream» connecting Russia-Turkey, as well as the «Nord Stream 1 and 2» connecting Russia-Germany were added in this century.

Azerbaijan's gas production increased by 3.8 % in 2023 to 48.5 billion cubic meters, while exports increased by 6.9 % to 23.8 billion cubic meters. Azerbaijan's Energy Minister Parviz Shahbazov said that the republic's plan is to increase gas production to 49 billion cubic meters in 2024, with exports reaching 24 billion cubic meters. And this plan is actually achievable, since Azerbaijan has already sold 4.1 billion cubic meters of gas in the first two months of 2024, of which 2.1 billion cubic meters were exported to Europe. Azerbaijan also wants to expand the list of European countries purchasing Azerbaijani gas, which currently includes Italy, Greece,

Bulgaria, Romania, Hungary and Serbia. For example, in 2026, Albania plans to start using Azerbaijani natural gas to meet its energy needs. According to information published by the international rating agency S&P Global Ratings, plans are currently being developed to develop the infrastructure necessary for gas distribution in Albania. This initiative will allow Albania to diversify its energy sources by using existing infrastructure, such as the Trans Adriatic Pipeline (TAP), reduce the country's dependence on hydroelectric power, and give Albania the opportunity to transit gas to European markets, including Italy. According to S&P, Albania will receive approximately 200 million cubic meters of Azerbaijani gas annually. This coincides with the planned first phase of the Trans Adriatic Pipeline (TAP) expansion, which will increase its capacity by an additional 1.2 billion cubic meters. Of this volume, 1 billion cubic meters is intended for Italy. At the same time, as a result of the expansion of TAP capacity, South-Eastern Europe will receive an additional 1.2 billion cubic meters of Azerbaijani gas by the end of 2025. In particular, from 2026, Italy will receive 1 billion cubic meters of this volume, and Albania will receive an additional 200 million cubic meters [18].

Tim McPhee, a representative of the European Commission's Directorate-General for Climate Change and Energy, stressed that the EU imports Caspian resources exclusively from Azerbaijan. The volume of gas imports from Russia to Azerbaijan is significantly less than Azerbaijan's exports to Europe, McPhee said. SOCAR Vice President Elshad Nasyrov also touched on the issue of re-export of Russian gas, pointing to the technical impossibility of loading gas other than Shah Deniz into the South Caucasus Pipeline. However, Azerbaijan has been importing gas from Russia since November 2022, which is used to meet the country's domestic needs, but this frees up more gas from the Shah Deniz field for export to European consumers, which strengthens Baku's position on the international market [18].

The role of the «vertical gas corridor» in the de-monopolization of the EU gas market. According to information published by the international rating agency S&P Global Ratings, plans to replace the RF with new energy sources are currently being implemented intensively everywhere. An example of this is the Balkan «vertical gas corridor» being created in southeastern Europe, that is, where the main regional market for Azerbaijani gas flows is located.

In January 2024, Ukraine, Moldova and Slovakia joined the EU's «Vertical Gas Corridor» project. The project, initiated by Greece, Bulgaria, Romania and Hungary, aims to strengthen the security of regional gas supplies for seven countries in Southeastern Europe and reduce their dependence on Russian gas. All countries have signed a memorandum of understanding on cooperation, which means that significant progress has been made in implementing the «corridor» plans (S&P GlobalRatings SE European gas transmission 2024).

The «corridor» would follow the existing route of the «Trans-Balkan Pipeline», built by the Soviet Union in the 1980s and already used to transport Russian gas southeast to Greece. However, the «vertical corridor» would deliver gas to the region from the opposite direction, south, allowing more countries to receive regasified liquefied natural gas (LNG) from the Greek coast via gas tankers.

Conclusion. Thus, the Russia-Ukraine war has further highlighted Georgia's geoeconomic importance in terms of demonopolizing the EU gas market. In particular:

- the hypothesis we expressed in the introduction to the article was confirmed. That the Russian-Ukrainian conflict resulted in the demonopolization of the South-Eastern European gas market. The place of the Gazprom JSC «Trans-Balkan Pipeline», which has been stopped since 2023, in the mentioned regional gas market will be taken by the «Vertical Gas Corridor» from the beginning of 2024, which becomes a direct competitor to the EU's «Southern Gas Corridor» passing through Georgia;

- in the context of the Russia-Ukraine war, the role of the «Southern Gas Corridor» as an alternative to the pipelines of JSC «Gazprom», and consequently, the transit importance of Georgia for the energy security of the European Union, will increase even more;

- the «vertical gas corridor» will partially limit the ability of the Caspian littoral countries to export energy resources to the world market via Georgia and will have a negative impact on the transit capabilities and stability of the region;

- in the conditions of intensified competition in the South-Eastern European gas market, it is necessary to design the supply of liquefied natural gas from Azerbaijan to Romania, with special attention to the construction of a degassing terminal at the port of Kulevi by SOCAR BST Ltd. (Georgia), i.e. the possibility of LNG production.

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